

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PROGRESSION OF GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS AND DYSFUNCTION OF THE PERIODONTAL VASCULAR ENDOTHELIUM**Zeynalov H.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
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Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10492244>**Abstract**

Periodontitis is a common chronic inflammatory disease characterized by the destruction of the tissues that contain the teeth. According to epidemiological studies, moderate periodontitis affects 40–60% of the adult population, while severe disease affects up to 10–15% [3]. The mutual influence between somatic diseases and dental pathology is associated with hemodynamic, metabolic, immunological and neurohumoral disorders in the body [4, 5, 6, 7]. A disease that directly affects the condition of periodontal tissues is diabetes mellitus (DM), which is one of the pressing problems of modern medicine.

Keywords: *generalized periodontitis, diabetes mellitus, endothelial dysfunction.*

This is explained by its significant prevalence, the severity of its course, and the seriousness of complications arising from it. As of 2016, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Ukraine averaged 9.1% (men – 8.3%, women – 9.7%) [8]. The prevalence of severe periodontitis is significantly higher in adults with HbA1c levels >9% compared to people without diabetes [11]. There is also a relationship between the degree of hyperglycemia and the severity of periodontitis. One of the early, frequent and prognostically unfavorable manifestations of diabetes is diabetic angiopathy, which develops as a result of long-term relative or absolute deficiency of insulin in the body [6, 14]. The most common idea is that periodontal pathology in patients with diabetes is a local manifestation of microangiopathy specific to diabetes. An important achievement in solving the pathogenesis of generalized periodontitis (GP) against the background of CD was the study of endothelial dysfunction (ED). Endothelial dysfunction is characterized by an imbalance between vasoconstriction and vasodilation factors in blood vessels and plays an important role in pathogenesis. is a 21-amino acid peptide that is a powerful vasoconstrictor produced by endothelial cells. It plays a role in the development of diseases such as hypertension and atherosclerosis. Preliminary studies identified ET-1 in gingival tissues of patients with HP [15]. Increased levels of circulating endothelin-1 (ET-1) have been identified in patients with diabetes, and a positive correlation has been demonstrated between plasma ET-1 levels and microangiopathy in patients with type II diabetes. envelope effect on nitric oxide (NO). Vascular DE may precede insulin resistance, although features of the insulin resistance syndrome include factors that have a negative impact on endothelial function. In addition, ET-1 induces a decrease in insulin sensitivity and may

be involved in the development of metabolic syndrome [16]. An important fact is that signs of DE increase with increasing duration of diabetes, which manifests itself in debilitation. reducing the dilating properties of the endothelium. Despite the variety of studies of endothelial functions in recent years, the mechanisms of development of DE in HP against the background of diabetes have not been sufficiently studied [12, 17]. The purpose of the study was to study the correlation between the clinical manifestations of HP, functional changes in its vascular system in patients with diabetes mellitus II and the severity of the disease.

Material and methods

A clinical and laboratory study was carried out on 34 patients with type II diabetes aged 40–65 years and 10 people without somatic pathology with clinically intact periodontium (comparison group). According to the taxonomy of periodontal diseases and M.F. Danilevsky, 16 patients were diagnosed with GP of initial and 1st degree, 11 patients – GP of 2nd degree, 7 people – GP of 3rd degree. Depending on the course of HP, 15 patients with chronic HP were examined, in whom diabetes was in the stage of compensation, and 19 patients with HP in the acute stage, in whom diabetes was in the stage of decompensation. The duration of diabetes averaged 12.5±2.42 years. Decompensation of diabetes was diagnosed in 19 (58.9%) patients, subcompensation in 15 (41.1%) patients. During diagnosis, generally accepted clinical methods were used, taking into account the results of the examination, in particular the presence of dental plaque, determination of the depth of periodontal pockets, the degree of recession, pathological mobility of teeth and traumatic occlusion.

To assess the prevalence and intensity of periodontal inflammatory processes, the PMA index (C. Parma, 1960), the dental plaque registration index

(O'Leary T., Drake R., Naylor J., 1972), as well as the BOP bleeding index (Ainamo, Bay) were used, 1975). Graphy and intraoral contact radiography. The object of immunological studies was rotovaridine (RR). Oral fluid was collected in the morning on an empty stomach by spitting into sterile tubes. The resulting substrates were centrifuged at 3000 rpm. within 15 min. For the studies, we used the supernatant liquid, which was stored in a freezer at -70°C . Supernatants were examined after thawing using STAT FAX 303 plus enzyme immunoassay analyzers. The concentration of ET-1 was determined using the Endothelin-1 ELISA system reagent kit produced by Biomedica (Austria). Patients with decompensated diabetes were treated as inpatients in the endocrinology departments of the 1st and 4th clinical hospitals in Lvov. Disorders of carbohydrate metabolism were determined by the level of fasting glycemia. The diagnosis of diabetes is considered established if the level of fasting glucose in the blood plasma increases by more than 7.0 mmol/l , and in the capillary blood plasma by more than 6.1 mmol/l [12]. Diabetes compensation was considered good when fasting glycemia was up to 9.0 mmol/l , subcompensation – at $9.0\text{--}12.0\text{ mmol/l}$, decompensation – more than 12.0 mmol/l . The stability of long-term compensation of diabetes was assessed by the content of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c). Its value in healthy individuals is 4–6% of total hemoglobin [12]. When HbA1c was 4–6%, compensation was considered good, 6–8.9% – subcompensation, 9% and above – decompensation. Statistical processing of the results was carried out using the Microsoft Office Excel application package. The probability indicator was assessed using Student's t-test

Research results

The results of a clinical instrumental examination of 34 patients with HP against the background of diabetes revealed significant changes in the indicators of the index assessment of the condition of periodontal tissues, which correlated with the severity, course of HD and greater HD and compensation of stage I. development up to $2.9\pm 0.06\text{ mm}$, with stage II GP. up to $4.6\pm 0.05\text{ mm}$, with stage III GP. – $7.2\pm 0.06\text{ mm}$, most often with serous-purulent exudate. RMA index for HP and st. was $50.3\pm 2.5\%$, with stage II HP. $56.3\pm 3.1\%$, with stage III HP. – $67.7\pm 2.9\%$. Dental plaque index (O'Leary et al., 1972) for stage I HP. development up to $34.9\pm 4.2\%$, with stage II HP. up to $59.8\pm 4.5\%$, with stage III GP. – $90.3\pm 7.2\%$. Bleeding index BOP in HP and art. development up to $41.5\pm 3.8\%$, with stage II HP. up to $62.7\pm 6.1\%$, with stage III HP. – $88.3\pm 5.5\%$. X-rays revealed osteoporosis and destruction of interdental membranes, a decrease in their height, and a mixed type of resorption predominated. tissues. An increase in the level of ET-1 in the examined patients indicates increased vasoconstriction, which is caused by increased secretion of endothelial-dependent constrictor factors. times higher than its level compared to the control group (0.42 ± 0.03 ; $p < 0.001$). Thus, a direct correlation is revealed between the level of ET-1, the severity of HP (Table 1) and the degree of compensation for diabetes (Table 2). Conclusion 1. In case of HP against the background of diabetes, a disturbance of en-

dothelium-dependent vascular relaxation and an increase in endothelial adhesiveness are observed in periodontal vessels. This encourages the development of severe vasoconstriction and a decrease in the intensity of local blood flow, which can cause increased platelet aggregation. The increase in the severity of the process in periodontal tissues during exacerbation of HP in patients with diabetes is accompanied by the development of DE, which is manifested by increased synthesis and release of the powerful vasoconstrictor ET-1 by the endothelium. ah periodontal. Determining the level of ET-1, a marker of endothelial dysfunction, can serve as a diagnostic test for the course of the pathological process and assess the effectiveness of treatment in patients with HP.2. As a result of the studies, the hygienic condition of the oral cavity in patients with type 2 diabetes corresponds to an unsatisfactory assessment, which contributes to the development of pathogenic microflora of the oral cavity and support of the inflammatory process. Therefore, all patients need effective prevention and treatment

Conclusions.

Determining the level of endothelin-1 in oral fluid can be a diagnostically significant factor for establishing the severity of the pathological process and the effectiveness of treatment in patients with generalized periodontitis against the background of diabetes mellitus.

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